

Evaluating Phytoplankton Diversity and Seasonal Trends in Chowfaldandi Khal, Bangladesh: A Step Towards Sustainable Mariculture

Shaibal Bhattacharjee^{a*}, Kazi Mohammad Reduanul Islam Shakil^a, Md. Imran Hossain Khan^a, Md. Shafiqul Islam^a

^aInstitute of Marine Sciences, Faculty of Marine Sciences and Fisheries, University of Chittagong, Chattogram 4331, Bangladesh

Correspondence

*Shaibal Bhattacharjee, Email: shawonimsfcubd@gmail.com

Abstract

Phytoplankton are the fundamental food source for higher trophic levels. They play a crucial role in the food chain/food web and the mariculture sector by providing direct food for zooplankton, fish, and other dependent animals. Considering the importance of the mariculture sector, this study assessed the composition of phytoplankton species, biodiversity, and abundance of the Chowfaldandi Khal at Cox's Bazar coast and explored their relationship to hydrological factors. Samples were collected during 2022-2023 using the transect method from the surface water of seven designated stations covering four seasons: winter (December-February), pre-monsoon (March-May), monsoon (June-August), and post-monsoon (September-November). We identified a total of 33 genera of phytoplankton under 4 divisions during the study period: Bacillariophyta (23), Chlorophyta (5), Cyanophyta (3), and Pyrrophyta (2). Some dominant genera found during the present study were *Biddulphia*, followed by *Coscinodiscus*, *Rhizosolenia*, and *Nostoc*. During the winter, the abundance of phytoplankton varied between 17098 and 24832 cells/liter, followed by pre-monsoon (12030–18292 cells/liter), post-monsoon (10631–14472 cells/liter), and monsoon (7676–12914 cells/liter), respectively. The values of the Shannon-Weiner diversity (H'), evenness (J'), and species richness (d) varied from 2.58-2.96, 0.92-0.95, and 1.53-2.39 in different seasons and ranged from 2.67 to 2.82, 0.92 to 0.96, and 1.78 to 2.15, respectively, at seven stations. Pearson's rank correlation found significant relationships between the phytoplankton community and hydrological factors. Understanding the dynamics of phytoplankton communities from this study will provide fundamental primary data for developing fixed management strategies that support sustainable mariculture practices, improve aquatic ecosystem health, and optimize resource utilization in this region.

Keywords: Phytoplankton diversity, abundance, composition, sustainable mariculture, seasonal trends, Bangladesh.